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MentorAI: An Intelligent Web-Based Learning Assistant Using Large Language Models

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ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence has significantly transformed the field of education. Traditional educational systems often fail to provide personalised and interactive learning experiences to students. To address this limitation, this research presents **MentorAI**, an intelligent web-based educational assistant designed to offer personalised academic guidance, real-time interaction, and adaptive learning support.

MentorAI integrates modern front-end technologies such as **HTML**, **CSS**, **JavaScript**, **Tailwind CSS**, and **Three.js**, together with **OpenRouter-based large language models (LLMs)** to provide dynamic tutoring capabilities. The platform supports multiple learning modes such as **concept explanation**, **step-by-step problem solving**, **quizzes**, and **concise summaries**. It also includes useful features such as **voice input**, **document summarisation**, **chat history management**, and **subject-based customisation**.

The system is designed to run entirely within the browser, ensuring a lightweight architecture while preserving user privacy through local storage mechanisms. This research paper discusses the system architecture, implementation methodology, functional modules, advantages, limitations, and future enhancements of the proposed platform.

The results demonstrate that MentorAI provides an effective and scalable educational support system capable of improving student engagement and accessibility.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Intelligent Tutoring System, Web Application, OpenRouter API, Personalised Learning, Large Language Models

Literature Review

1. **AI-Based Personalized E-Learning Systems: Issues, Challenges, and Solutions:** <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9840390>
2. **Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Review:** <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9069875>
3. **Application and Development Prospect of Monitoring Screen based on Three.js Unit Equipment Control System:** <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10076962>
4. **Learn Three.js: Program 3D animations and visualizations for the web with JavaScript and WebGL:** <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10162774>
5. **OpenRouter: OpenFlow extension and implementation based on a commercial router:** <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6089045>
6. **Comparative Analysis of AI Chatbot for Assessing Gemini AI, DeepSeek AI, and Qwen AI via OpenRouter API Integration:** <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/11134904>

1. INTRODUCTION

The education sector is increasingly adopting intelligent technologies to make learning more interactive, personalised, and accessible. Traditional classroom learning often suffers from limitations such as fixed teaching pace, lack of individual attention, and limited accessibility outside classroom hours.

Artificial Intelligence has emerged as a promising solution to overcome these limitations. AI-powered tutoring systems can simulate human-like interaction, adapt responses according to student requirements, and provide immediate assistance.

This project introduces **MentorAI**, a web-based intelligent tutoring platform designed to serve as a digital academic companion. Unlike conventional chatbots, MentorAI focuses specifically on learning assistance. It provides:

- subject-specific academic help
- explanation of concepts
- stepwise solutions
- quiz-based learning
- summarisation of educational content

The main objective of this project is to create a lightweight, interactive, and scalable AI tutor that can be easily accessed through a web browser.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In real world students often face the following challenges:

- Lack of personalised attention in traditional learning environments where teachers can't pay attention to a single individual student.
- Many students face difficulty understanding different complex topics at their own pace.
- Students are not able to access academic assistance outside the class hours.
- Students need adaptive explanation styles based on learning preference

Existing online resources provide information but often lack **interactive educational guidance**.

Therefore, there is a need for a system that can provide:

- personalised tutoring
- interactive dialogue
- multi-mode explanation
- easy accessibility

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

The main objectives of MentorAI are:

1. To develop an AI-powered educational assistant accessible via web browsers/
2. To provide multiple tutoring modes for different learning needs.
3. To integrate LLM-based intelligent response generation.
4. To maintain conversation history locally for continuity.
5. To allow subject-based contextual learning.
6. To provide document summarisation support.
7. To enhance accessibility through voice interaction.

4.LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of artificial intelligent tutoring systems has been an active area of research for many years.

4.1. INTELLIGENT TUTORING SYSTEMS

Traditional intelligence tutoring systems focus on domain knowledge and adaptive feedback. However, many older systems are rule-based and not flexible.

4.2. CONVERSATIONAL AI IN EDUCATION

Recent developments in LLMs such as GPT-style systems have enabled natural language interaction and dynamic explanation generation.

4.3. WEN-BASED LEARNING PLATFORMS

Modern educational systems increasingly use browser-based delivery for accessibility and platform independence.

MentorAI combines these research directions by merging:

- conversational intelligence
- tutoring-specific workflows
- lightweight web deployment

5.PROPOSED SYSTEM

This project, MentorAI consists two main interfaces:

5.1. LANDING PAGE

The launching page acts as the project's presentation interface. It is the first page that you will see. It provides:

- Project introduction
- Feature highlights
- Smooth animations
- Navigation to the tutor system

It uses Three.js-based animated background rendering to improve visual engagement.

5.2. TUTOR INTERFACE

The main tutoring system in MentorAI contains the following features:

Subject Selection

- General
- Math

- Science
- Programming
- History
- Language
- Arts
- Business

Tutor Mode

- Explain Mode— concept explanation
- Step-by-step Mode— procedural solutions
- Quiz Mode— knowledge testing
- Summary Mode— concise learning output

API Integration

The system uses OpenRouter API to access language models dynamically. Users can even choose different LLM models manually.

6. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

6.1. Front-End Layer

The front-end layer is developed using:

- HTML
- CSS

- JavaScript
- Tailwind CSS

6.2. Application Logic Layer

JavaScript controls:

- Chat management
- Tutor mode switching
- API request generation
- Voice input
- Document processing
- Local storage management

6.3. AI Processing Layer

- User queries
- Context-based prompts
- Subject-specific tutoring responses

6.4. Storage Layer

- Chat history
- API configuration
- Selected model
- Selected subject
- User preferences

This design allows continuity without server-side databases.

7.METHODOLOGY

The development methodology followed was modular front-end engineering.

8.FUNCTIONAL MODULES

8.1. Chat Management Module

Handles sending, receiving, rendering, and storing messages.

8.2. Subject Context Module

Adjusts AI response behaviour based on selected academic subject.

8.3. Tutor Mode Module

Changes prompt strategy based on learning mode.

8.4. Voice Input Module

Uses browser speech recognition for hands-free interaction.

8.5. File Summarisation Module

Allows uploading text-based files and summarising their content.

8.6. API Configuration Module

Enables model selection and API key management.

9.RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The developed system successfully demonstrates the following:

Observed Results

- Smooth interactive UI
- Real-time tutoring interface
- Subject-specific learning support
- Multi-mode tutoring flexibility
- Local persistence of chat sessions
- Voice and file input support

Educational Benefits

- Improves self-paced learning
- Enhances concept clarity
- Supports personalised study behaviour
- Reduces dependency on fixed classroom schedules

The project shows that modern browser-based LLM tutoring can be highly practical.

10.ADVANTAGES OF THIS PROJECT(MentorAI)

MentorAI offers several advantages:

- lightweight architecture
- no backend dependency for core storage
- browser accessibility
- personalised learning interaction
- flexible tutoring styles
- scalable API-based AI integration
- modern user experience

11.LIMITATIONS

Despite its strengths, some limitations exist:

- Depends on internet connection for live AI responses
- Accuracy depends on selected language model
- No backend database for cloud synchronisation
- Limited document format support
- No analytics dashboard for learning performance

12.FUTURE SCOPE

Future enhancements may include:

- user authentication system

- cloud-based conversation sync
- learning progress tracking
- adaptive difficulty analysis
- multilingual tutoring
- handwritten problem solving
- OCR-based image understanding
- teacher dashboard integration

These additions could transform MentorAI into a full-scale intelligent educational platform.

13. CONCLUSION

This research presented **MentorAI**, an intelligent browser-based tutor assistant powered by LLM (Large Language Model).

The system successfully combines:

- interactive tutoring
- subject-aware assistance
- multiple learning modes
- voice interaction
- document summarisation
- local data persistence

The implementation demonstrates that AI can significantly improve accessibility, flexibility, and personalisation in learning. MentorAI serves as a practical example of how conversational AI can be integrated into education to create effective digital learning companions.

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